

List of Definitions and Additional Readings

I. Exploring Digital Servitization to Overcome the Digitalization Paradox

Terminology	Definition	Reference
Digitalization	Digitalization is the use of digital technologies to change a business model and provide new revenue and value-producing opportunities; digitalization is the process of moving to a digital business.	Gartner. (2019). Gartner glossary >digitalization. Available at: https://www.gartner.com/en/information-technology/glossary/digitalization
Digitalization paradox	It is a situation in which companies invest in digitalization but struggle to earn the expected revenue growth.	Gebauer, H., Fleisch, E., Lamprecht, C., & Wortmann, F. (2020). Growth paths for overcoming the digitalization paradox. <i>Business Horizons</i> , 63(3), 313-323.
Productivity paradox	The productivity paradox highlights how ICT investments often do not lead to the expected productivity or cost improvements.	Stratopoulos, T., & Dehning, B. (2000). Does successful investment in information technology solve the productivity paradox? <i>Information and Management</i> , 38(2), 103 - 117
Servitization	Servitization is defined as a transition, where the company moves from providing pure stand-alone products and add-on services to maintenance contracts, operational services and, finally, to outcome- or performance-based offerings.	Huikkola, T., Kohtamäki, M., 2018. Business models in servitization (Eds.) In: Kohtamäki, M., Baines, T.S., Rabetino, R., Bigdeli, A.Z. (Eds.), Practices and Tools For servitization: Managing service Transition. London: Palgrave McMillan, pp. 61–81.
Digital servitization	Digital servitization is defined as a transition process from pure products and add-on services to smart product-service systems.	Kohtamäki, M., Parida, V., Patel, P. C., & Gebauer, H. (2020). The relationship between digitalization and servitization: The role of servitization in capturing the financial potential of digitalization. <i>Technological Forecasting and Social Change</i> , 151, 119804.
Business model	A business model describes an architecture for how a firm creates and delivers value to customers and the mechanisms employed to capture a share of that value	Teece, D.J. (2018), “Business models and dynamic capabilities”, Long Range Planning, Vol. 51 No. 1, pp. 40-49.

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II. Transforming Modern Healthcare with Blockchain

Terminology	Definition	Reference
Blockchain technology	Blockchain technology is identified as a distributed ledger technology for peer-to-peer (P2P) network digital data transactions that may be publicly or privately distributed to all users, allowing any type of data to be stored in a reliable and verifiable way	Khezr, S., Moniruzzaman, M., Yassine, A., & Benlamri, R. (2019). Blockchain technology in healthcare: A comprehensive review and directions for future research. <i>Applied sciences</i> , 9(9), 1736.

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III. Towards Legal Compliance of Information Systems

Terminology	Definition	Reference
Regulatory requirements	Regulatory requirements are requirements that are derived from mandatory public norms contained in laws and other regulations.	Y. Maley. 1994. The language of the law. <i>Language and the Law</i> 11 (1994), 25.
Regulatory norms	Regulatory norms are the logical units of regulations usually containing a single regulatory statement.	Kosenkov, O., Unterkalmsteiner, M., Mendez, D., & Fucci, D. (2021). Vision for an Artefact-based Approach to Regulatory Requirements Engineering. In <i>Proceedings of 15th International Symposium on</i>

		<i>Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement (ESEM)</i> (pp. 1-6).
Requirements engineering	RE is defined as the subfield of software engineering pertaining to eliciting, modeling, analyzing, communicating, agreeing and evolving requirements.	B. Nuseibeh and S. Easterbrook, "Requirements engineering: a roadmap," <i>Proceedings of the Conference on The Future of Software Engineering</i> , 2000, pp. 35–46.
Nonfunctional requirements	Nonfunctional requirements, also known as quality attributes, are the behavioral qualities that a system must possess including reliability, usability, maintainability and so on.	Gross, D., & Yu, E. (2001). From non-functional requirements to design through patterns. <i>Requirements Engineering</i> , 6(1), 18-36.
Cognitive biases	Cognitive biases are defined as psychological phenomena that prejudice decision quality in a significant number of decisions for a significant number of people.	Arnott, D. 2006. Cognitive biases and decision support systems development: a design science approach. <i>Information Systems Journal</i> . 16, 1, 55–78.
Framing effect	Framing effect is the tendency to give different responses to problems that have surface dissimilarities but that are really formally identical.	K. E. Stanovich, <i>What intelligence tests miss: The psychology of rational thought</i> . Yale University Press, 2009.
Debiasing	Debiasing is the process of inhibiting or removing the effects of biases.	Larrick, R.P.: <i>Debiasing</i> . In: <i>Blackwell Handbook of Judgment and Decision Making</i> . pp. 316-338. <i>Blackwell Publishing Ltd</i> (2008)
Socio-technical interventions	It is a method, practice, technique, tool, program or concept that changes the behavior of one or more participants in a software project	Ralph, P. (2011). Toward a theory of debiasing software development. In <i>EuroSymposium on Systems Analysis and Design</i> (pp. 92-105). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.

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